

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

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Protocol for decontamination of growing substrate and disposal of infected plant material

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D5.3 - Protocol for decontamination of growing substrate and disposal of infected plant material

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY.....	5
2	INTRODUCTION.....	6
3	STEAMING IN GERMANY.....	7
4	SOLARISATION IN SPAIN.....	12
5	SOLARISATION IN ISRAEL.....	16
6	LUMINEX AND BIOASSAYS BY WAGENINGEN RESEARCH.....	19

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

°C: degrees Celsius

Cl-TSP: chlorinated Trisodium Phosphate

DCM: De Ceuster Meststoffen

LNW: Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen

PCR: polymerase chain reaction

TEC: Fundacion para las Tecnologias auxiliares de la Agricultura (TECNOVA)

ToBRFV: tomato brown rugose fruit virus

TMV: tobacco mosaic virus

ToMV-O3: tomato mosaic virus strain Ohio 3

WR: Wageningen Research

VC: Volcani Center

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The goal of work package 5.3 is the identification of methods to eradicate tobamoviruses in contaminated growing media. Specifically, the application of heat was investigated. Two methods were tested: steaming and solarisation.

Steaming is an approved method to sanitize soil, pots and plant growing media. In Germany, LNW found that temperatures of more than 90 °C are effective to inactivate the tobamovirus tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) in contaminated growing substrate. The core temperature of the substrate should be kept at > 90 °C for at least 20 minutes if moist heat is applied. However, dry heat requires heat application for several hours.

The solarisation method takes advantage of naturally high temperatures in the Mediterranean region in summer.

In Israel (VC) the solarization experiments were performed twice with ToBRFV contaminated substrate. In 2023 the results could not be concluded due to the war situation after October 7th. Therefore, a new experiment was conducted in the summer of 2024 and the final evaluation of the results is expected later. The tested treatments were: solarization, solarization in combination with an application of the disinfectant chlorinated Trisodium Phosphate (Cl-TSP; 2 weeks later), Cl-TSP alone, a positive control (no solarization) and a negative control.

Solarisation in Spain conducted by TEC in the autumn of 2022 demonstrated that lower temperatures might be sufficient to inactivate the related tobamovirus TMV in cocopeat substrate. A solarisation process of sixty days was appropriate to inactivate TMV if organic material was incorporated into the bags to increase temperatures during solarisation. When substrate was solarized without organic material, lower temperatures were reached and the contaminated substrate was found to still contain infectious TMV. This indicates that higher temperatures are needed to fully deactivate the virus and caution should be practiced to apply solarization under the correct conditions.

TEC, VC, and LNW used bioassays to prove that tobamovirus was successfully eradicated from the contaminated substrate. The bioassays were performed by growing healthy susceptible plants in steamed or solarized growing substrate. While the bio-assays confirmed the success of the applied eradication methods, this validation process is very time-consuming. The newly developed Luminex method by WR is much faster and easier to perform. This molecular method was developed to distinguish between infectious and non-infectious virus and is based on the specific multiplex detection of the presence or absence of intact (= infectious) RNA of TMV or tomato mosaic virus (ToMV). Luminex results were verified in bioassays by inoculation of disinfection trials on *Nicotiana glutinosa*, a local lesion host for tobamoviruses.

2 INTRODUCTION

ToBRFV particles, like those of other tobamoviruses, are very stable and can survive for long periods in infected debris, soil or on contaminated surfaces, making it difficult to sanitize soil and growing media after ToBRFV outbreaks. The application of disinfecting chemicals is connected to some disadvantages. Only a limited number of products are effective against ToBRFV. Additionally, disinfectant residue may remain present in the growing medium, which later can affect growth of the plants.

Disinfection of soil and plant substrate by heat is an alternative to the application of disinfecting chemicals. This includes solarisation and steaming. Steaming is a proven and widely used method for disinfection of substrates and gardening devices. However, tobamoviruses are highly persistent and heat stable. The aim of our studies was to investigate if solarisation and steaming can create conditions that are sufficient to eradicate infectious tobamoviruses in growing media like cocopeat substrate.

ELISA and RT-PCR are standard methods to detect the presence of viruses. However, they are not able to distinguish between infectious and inactivated viruses. Thus, during the steaming and solarisation experiments, a bioassay by growing healthy plants in treated substrate was conducted to verify the successful inactivation of the tobamoviruses. However, bioassays are laborious and time-consuming.

The Luminex approach is a faster and easier molecular method and was adapted to detect and distinguish infectious from inactivated (= non-infectious) virus. The Luminex method is based on the simultaneous detection of multiple large fragments of genetic material (RNA). The presence of multiple large fragments is a strong indication for the intactness of virus RNA and a proxy for the infectiousness of the virus. For the purpose of the project, the method was specifically designed for the detection of ToMV/TMV. The solarization trials performed by TEC and the steaming trials performed at LNW were both performed with a particular tobamovirus isolate designated tomato mosaic virus Ohio III (ToMV-O3, McRitchie and Alexander, 1962, *Phytopathology* 53: 394-398) from the plant virus collection at WR, as an alternative for ToBRFV to avoid phytosanitary risks associated with the regulated virus ToBRFV. ToMV-O3 is a typical tobamovirus and in its physical characteristics comparable to ToBRFV. The reliability of the Luminex test in predicting presence or absence of ToMV-O3 infectivity was confirmed and validated through various bioassays.

3 STEAMING IN GERMANY

Steaming is used to sanitize soil, growing media and other devices such as pots in horticulture. ToBRFV and other tobamoviruses are known to be very heat stable. Thus, high temperatures are required to inactivate these viruses.

Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen (LNW) performed three experiments to investigate the effect of steaming on tobamovirus survival in growing media. In all three experiments, temperatures of > 90 °C were used. In experiment 1, LNW applied moist heat for two periods: 20 and 40 minutes, respectively. In experiments 2 and 3, LNW applied dry heat for approximately five hours. The conditions of all three experiments proved to be suitable to eradicate the virus from the media.

3.1 Experiment 1

3.1.1 Material and methods

3.1.1.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-infected substrate

Semi-purified ToMV-O3 inoculum (tomato mosaic virus from Prime Diagnostics, WR) was used to infest tomato plants cv. 'Moneymaker'. However, a molecular analysis suggested (see paragraph 6.1) that the virus supplied by WR from its virus collection, was actually an isolate of TMV (tobacco mosaic virus) instead of ToMV (tomato mosaic virus). As ToMV and TMV are physically and serologically very closely related, it was concluded that this will not affect the set-up of the trials nor the expected results. For clarity in the following section of the report the virus used for inoculation will be referred to as ToMV-O3.

Young healthy tomato plants of cv. 'Moneymaker' were transplanted to bags (100x20x10cm; length/width/height) containing a growing medium (50% cocopeat and 50% husk chips). Per bag three young plants were transplanted. Infection was conducted by dusting two leaves with celite and gently rubbing extracts of ToMV-O3-infected plants on two leaves of the seedlings. After five to ten minutes of incubation time, the leaves were rinsed with distilled water. Thirty-six bags of substrate were used, of which nine were planted with uninfected plants to be used as a negative control. ToMV-O3-infected and healthy tomato plants were cultivated for four months in a greenhouse according to common practice. The infection status of plants was verified via ELISA with polyclonal antibodies specific for detection of the used ToMV-O3 isolate, with two analyses after approximately six weeks of the inoculation and by the end of the cultivation period.

At the end of the cultivation period, plants were not watered anymore to facilitate their disposal. This also led to the substrate being dried out. Plants were removed before steaming. However, some roots remained in the medium.

3.1.1.2 Steaming

Six of the bags with infected plants and three bags with healthy plants were kept as non-steamed control. Using the remaining bags, we tested two exposure times. One half of the bags was steamed at >90 °C for 20 minutes and the other half was steamed for 40 minutes, respectively. The bags were arranged in one layer to enable complete steam penetration. A probe was inserted into the bags to monitor the temperature.

3.1.1.3 Bioassay

Virus-free tomato seedlings were transplanted to steamed bags and non-steamed control bags. Three plants per bag were transplanted. Visible symptoms of tobamovirus infection were evaluated regularly. The infection status of the plants was assessed using the ELISA method at four and ten weeks after transplantation, respectively. Additionally, a biotest was conducted by gently rubbing extracts of the media on leaves of *Nicotiana tabacco* cv. 'Xanthi' seventeen weeks after transplantation. *N. tabacco* 'Xanthi' was chosen as it is a local lesion host which forms characteristic lesions within 5-7 days after exposure to infection with Tobamovirus.

Figure 1. Growing of tobamovirus-infected plants (1), steaming procedure (2) and subsequent bioassay in the greenhouse (3).

3.1.2 Results

3.1.2.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-infected substrate

Tobamovirus-infected plants were tested positive for ToMV-O3 by the ELISA method and not infected plants were tested negative for ToMV-O3.

3.1.2.2 Steaming

Temperatures of > 90 °C were reached for 40 minutes but only for 17 minutes in the shorter treatment instead of 20 minutes. We observed a high absorbance of water by the medium.

3.1.2.3 Bioassay

Symptoms of tobamovirus infection became visible on tomato plants grown in non-steamed virus-contaminated substrate after three weeks. In contrast, plants that were grown in steamed substrate or substrate without previous virus-infection remained symptom-free until to the end of the bioassay, seventeen weeks after transplantation. The status of virus infection was confirmed by ELISA method.

Tobacco plants displayed necrotic lesions within one week on leaves that were treated with Tobamovirus contaminated non-steamed media. Leaves that were treated with steamed media or media without previous virus-infection remained symptom-free (no local lesions observed).

On most steamed media, a heavy growth of fungi and bacteria was observed during the bioassay. The heat treatment had destroyed most of the microorganisms in the substrate. In the bioassay, the bags were not kept under sterile conditions so that the first occurring bacteria and fungi could multiply unhindered. It was expected that naturally occurring microorganisms would eventually re-colonize the substrate.

Figure 2. Plants with virus symptoms in not steamed control bags (left), plant without symptoms in 20 minutes steamed bags (right) in the bioassay.

3.2 Experiments 2 and 3

3.2.1 Material and methods

3.2.1.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate

The generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate was conducted as described for experiment 1, except that we used bifurcated tomato plants in experiment 3.

3.2.1.2 Steaming

To use conditions that are closer to common practice, the bags were piled and steamed at $> 90^{\circ}\text{C}$ for five hours. However, this prevented the steam from penetrating all bags, meaning that the bags in the middle were exposed to dry heat instead of moist heat. In experiment 3, six of the contaminated bags and three bags with healthy plants were kept as non-steamed control. In experiment 2, we found control bags which should not be infected being contaminated with the virus, possibly by whiteflies. Therefore, twenty-seven contaminated bags were steamed and nine contaminated bags were not steamed.

3.2.1.3 Bioassay

Healthy tomato seedlings were transplanted to steamed and non-steamed substrate bags. Symptoms of virus infection were assessed regularly. Six and ten weeks after transplantation, leaf samples were taken and virus infection was assessed via ELISA. Plants were observed for 14 weeks.

3.2.2 Results

3.2.2.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate

In both experiments, we found mild symptoms of ToMV-O3 infection, mainly on auxillary branches of the inoculated tomato plants. The presence of ToMV-O3 was confirmed via ELISA. No symptoms appeared on not infected control plants of experiment 3 and no virus could be detected.

However, in experiment 2, ToMV-O3 was detected in plants that were not inoculated. This partial contamination of controls may occur when manipulating highly stable tobamoviruses. In particular there was a heavy infestation with whiteflies (*Trialeurodes vaporariorum*) during this experiment. We suspect that the insects might have accidentally transferred the virus mechanically. The plants developed more and finer roots in experiment 3 compared to experiment 2.

3.2.2.2 Bioassay

We observed growth of fungi and bacteria in many bags after steaming. This was most severe in the first two or three weeks after the beginning of the bioassay (Figure 3).

After three weeks, symptoms on some of the tomato plants that were grown in tobamovirus-contaminated non-steamed substrate became visible. In contrast, no symptoms of virus infection were visible on tomatoes that were grown in steamed media or in the non-contaminated control. However, some plants displayed yellowing, possibly due to nutrient deficiency. Additional fertilizer was applied to these plants. Afterwards, newly grown leaves were without symptoms. An ELISA test showed that plants that grew in not-steamed contaminated bags were positive for ToMV-O3 and plants that grew in steamed bags were negative for ToMV-O3.

Samples of remaining roots from previously grown infected tomato plants were taken immediately before and after steaming. Some of them were analysed by WR (see chapter 6). The results show that infectious virus particles remained present in the roots. Finally, it is relevant to mention that the protocol was validated in practice by PCH on ToBRFV contaminated substrate and proved to be efficient to deactivate the virus.

Figure 3. Growth of fungi and bacteria in many bags after steaming.

3.3 Discussion

Our experiments show that steaming at $> 90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is a feasible method to deactivate the tobamovirus in growing media in a way that the medium may be reused. Taking into account studies within and outside Virtigation, the application of heat under moist conditions seems to be a safe method to inactivate tobamoviruses. Exposure times of 20 minutes are likely sufficient to inactivate tobamoviruses under moist conditions.

Dry conditions require longer exposure times and/or higher temperatures. Exposure to dry heat at $> 90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for five hours successfully reduced the inoculum of tobamoviruses up to a point that the susceptible tomato cultivar was not infected when grown in treated media. However, tests conducted by WR showed that infectious virus particles may remain in the roots of previously grown infected plants. But it is difficult to infect tomato plants through the roots with ToBRFV. VC found that in contaminated soil, only 2% of the plants become infected. Our Protocol was validated in practice by PCH on ToBRFV contaminated substrate and proved to be efficient to deactivate the virus. Thus, our trial proves that the amount of virus is sufficiently reduced. However, as long as active virus remains in the substrate, infection may break through later in the crop cycle. Therefore, the degree of tobamovirus reduction by dry heat remains to be investigated to clarify whether this reduction is sufficient to safely prevent the infection of susceptible plants.

The heat not only inactivated the viruses but had a severe impact on the microbiome of the medium. Most beneficial microorganisms are likely killed by the heat. Thus, other microorganisms, including potentially harmful fungi and bacteria, might establish after steaming because of the absence of antagonists. We saw this in all three experiments. Thus, application of beneficiary microorganisms and/or soil activators to the substrate after steaming is advisory.

4 SOLARISATION IN SPAIN

Solarisation takes advantage of high temperatures and solar radiation in the Mediterranean region. The purpose of this experiment conducted by TECNOVA was to investigate if solarisation can create sufficiently high temperatures to eradicate tobamoviruses in growing media through radiation heat. Tomato plants were infected with ToMV-O3 to create tobamovirus-contaminated growing media. The media were solarized for sixty days during autumn 2022 in Spain. During this time, the conditions for solarisation resemble those of Central Europe in summer. A bioassay showed that no virus was present in most plants that grew in the solarized media. However, in some samples, ToMV-O3 was detected by a PCR-based method. Thus, the method seems not appropriate to completely eradicate the virus.

4.1 Material and methods

4.1.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate

In spring, to start the experiment during hot summer times, healthy tomato plants were inoculated with a tobamovirus inoculum (ToMV-O3 from Prime Diagnostics, WR, see also chapter 3.1) in multiple experiments. However, no symptoms were observed in leaves and the virus could not be detected by ToBRFV ImmunoStrip (Agdia; which can identify tobamovirus-infected plants), suggesting that the inoculum was not infectious under the initial experimental conditions.

Finally, new tomato plants were inoculated in July. Two different methodologies were performed to obtain virus inoculum: T1 and T2. To prepare the virus inoculum T1, semi-purified ToMV-O3 (Prime Diagnostics) was mixed with phosphate buffer, distilled water, and polyvinylpyrrolidone. To prepare T2, Tobamovirus-susceptible tobacco plants were infected with ToMV-O3 inoculum. Then, fresh ToMV-O3 infected leaf material was extracted and mixed with T1 inoculum solution. The inoculum was prepared with phosphate buffer and polyvinylpyrrolidone.

A total of 50 tomato plants cv. 'Moneymaker', which is susceptible to ToMV-O3 and other tobamoviruses, were inoculated twice by lightly dusting two leaves per plant with carborundum powder and gently rubbing inoculum with a sterile swab. The first inoculation was performed 15 days after sowing when the seedlings had 3 to 4 leaves. The second inoculation was performed approximately 40 days after sowing.

Eighteen healthy plants of tobamovirus resistant cv. 'Alvalade RZ' served as negative control and 12 tobacco plants were inoculated with ToMV-O3 to create a positive control. After the first inoculation, 28 days after sowing, the plants were transplanted to cocopeat substrate bags in the greenhouse. Three plants per bag were utilised. First symptoms of virus infection were observed in August and the presence of ToMV-O3 was confirmed by ImmunoStrips.

4.1.2 Solarisation

The need to select an adequate tobamovirus isolate for the experiments and subsequent problems for its detection in infected plants led to a delay of the solarisation process. Thus, it was not possible to test as many solarisation durations and timings as planned, and a representative treatment was

chosen. The solarisation was performed from 9th September to 9th November, so for approximately 8 weeks. Three bags with ToMV-O3-infected ‘Moneymaker’ plants were not solarised and kept as control.

To check if the presence of organic infected material influences the efficacy of the solarisation process, one of the following two treatments was applied to the bags prior to solarisation:

- i) The aerial parts of the plants were cut, but the roots were kept inside the bag, and additional ToMV-O3 infected leaves were added to supplement.
- ii) The complete plants including the roots were pulled out of the bags.

The solarisation was performed by completely closing the ridge and side windows of the greenhouse and wrapping the bags in transparent 37.5 µm thick polyethylene plastic film (Figure 4). Finally, the cocopeat bags were moistened with water. Positive control bags of infected tomato plants ‘Moneymaker’ and tobacco plants were removed and stored. The temperature inside of each cocopeat bag was recorded by a temperature logger Tempmate M1. The logger was protected with a plastic bag from water and inserted in the middle of the cocopeat bag.

Figure 4. Infected plants in bags before solarization and subsequent solarization of wrapped bags.

4.1.3 Biotest

Eight days after the end of the 8-week solarization period, healthy tomato seedlings were transplanted to the solarised bags. Seedlings of cv. “Moneymaker” were planted into bags where plants of the same variety were cultivated previously and “Alvalade RZ” plants were grown in bags of previously cultivated “Alvalade RZ” plants. Three plants per bag were utilised.

Cocopeat bags that were not ToMV-O3 contaminated and had not been solarised were added to the greenhouse as negative controls. The following plants were grown in these bags:

- Healthy ‘Alvalade Rz’ plants
- Healthy ‘Moneymaker’ plants
- Healthy tobacco plants

To detect if ToMV-O3 was present, all tomato plants were tested for ToMV-O3 with ImmunoStrips seven weeks after transplantation. Eight weeks after transplantation, the leaves of tomato plants which grew in the solarised bags were used to prepare an inoculum. The next day, the inoculation of

healthy young tobacco plants was performed as described previously. Six weeks after inoculation, the tobacco plants were tested on the presence of ToMV-O3 by using ImmunoStrips.

Additionally, pooled samples from plants that grew in solarised bags and pooled samples from substrate were analysed on the presence of ToMV-O3 by RT-PCR by Scientia Terrae. Furthermore, a bio-assay was performed at Scientia Terrae with the local lesion host *N. tabacum* 'Xanthi' to confirm infectivity of the virus in case of a positive PCR test. Leaves from three plants that grew in the same bag were pooled for sampling. Similarly, substrate from the same treatment (solarisation with or without residual crop) was combined.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate

In July, tomato plants cv. 'Moneymaker' and tobacco plants were inoculated with semi-purified ToMV-O3 or a mix of ToMV-O3 and infected leaf material, respectively. The tobacco plants showed severe symptoms of tobamovirus infection in July 28th, whilst the tomato plants displayed mild symptoms on August 24th. On September 6th, the ToMV-O3 was detected by TMV ImmunoStrips. All strips tested positive for infected tobacco and tomato plants, regardless of the inoculum that was used. This means that both inoculation procedures are valid and none is more effective (i.e., symptoms appear earlier or are more severe) than the other.

4.2.2 Temperatures during solarisation

During the 60 days of solarisation, the average temperatures lay between 27.5 °C and 28.7°C. The maximum temperatures ranged from 42.1 °C to 46.2 °C. Temperatures of > 40 °C inside the bags were reached for a period of 6 to 34 days (Figure 5). The temperatures in bags with residual roots and leaves reached higher maximum temperatures than those without residual crops. On average, maximum temperatures of bags with residual crop were 45.2 °C and temperatures of > 40 °C were reached on 23.0 days. In contrast, in bags without residual crop, maximum temperatures were on average 42.9 °C and > 40 °C was reached only on 9.2 days.

4.2.3 Bioassay after solarisation

Eight days after solarisation (17th November), healthy tomato seedlings were transplanted to the solarised bags. Leaves of the transplanted plants were used to inoculate tobacco eight weeks after transplantation to check for the presence of infectious virus. The tomato and tobacco plants were tested for the presence of ToMV-O3 with ImmunoStrips. All tests were negative. Additionally, a molecular analysis was performed by PCR and confirmed the absence of ToMV-O3 in most plants. However, two samples from plants that grew in substrate that was solarized in bags without residual crop were positive for ToMV-O3 when analyzed by PCR but not by ImmunoStrips, possibly due to a low concentration of virus. A bio-assay performed with tobacco plants confirmed the infectivity of the virus found by PCR test.

During 133 days of cultivation in the solarized bags, the tomato plants showed no symptoms of virus infection, except two plants. These two plants with symptoms were tested positive for TYLCV, but were

negative for ToMV-O3. However, by the end of the experiment, many plants exhibited dry leaves on the base of the plant, wilting, or curling of leaves, but not mosaic symptoms. Plants that were tested positive for ToMV-O3 displayed curling of leaves.

LOGGER	LINE-BAG	TREATMENT	Tmax (°C)	Tmin (°C)	Tave (°C)
1	1-1	A	44.0	15.6	27.8
2	1-2	EG	44.9	15.5	28.1
3	1-3	EG	44.6	16.0	28.0
4	2-1	A	43.6	15.6	28.0
5	2-2	DF	42.8	16.3	28.3
6	2-3	DF	42.8	16.3	28.3
7	3-1	A	44.0	15.8	27.6
8	3-2	E	45.3	15.4	28.0
9	3-3	E	44.7	15.7	27.9
10	3-4	E	44.9	15.7	27.9
11	4-1	A	43.0	16.0	28.3
12	4-2	D	43.2	15.9	28.2
13	4-3	D	43.0	16.2	28.3
14	4-4	D	42.3	16.2	27.9
15	5-1	A	44.5	15.3	27.7
16	5-2	G	45.0	15.8	28.0
17	5-3	G	45.9	16.1	28.7
18	5-4	G	46.2	15.2	27.8
20	6-1	A	43.1	15.4	27.6
21	6-2	F	42.4	15.2	27.3
22	6-3	F	43.3	16.2	28.2
23	6-4	F	43.8	15.6	27.9
24	6-5	F	42.1	15.5	27.5

Figure 5. Temperatures during solarisation in the TEC solarization trial.

4.3 Discussion

In this experiment, TECNOVA aimed to test multiple variations of the solarisation method, differing in timing of start and duration. The experiment was supposed to be conducted during summer. However, due to the difficulties to select an adequate tobamovirus isolate for generating contaminated substrate and subsequent problems in the detection systems in infected plants, the solarisation process was delayed and it could not start before September. Thus, it was not possible precluding to test many different solarisation periods and timings. Despite the relatively low temperatures that were reached during the experiment, a solarisation of sixty days eradicated tobamoviruses in growing media in most cases. Residual crop material was probably instrumental to increase the maximum temperature inside the bags, and consequently the number of days on which the medium was heated to > 40 °C. Thus, residual crop and/or the introduction of organic debris may be an adequate way to increase the efficacy and efficiency of the solarisation process. In contrast, the absence of residual crop led to lower temperatures inside the bags that were not sufficient to eradicate ToMV-O3 in all bags. Thus, more research should be done to confirm under which treatment conditions solarisation can be safely used to better eradicate the virus in substrate in the Mediterranean region. It is expected that a solarisation process during summer might lead to temperatures that are sufficient in media without the addition of residual crop materials, because the outside temperatures and light intensity are much higher during summer.

5 SOLARISATION IN ISRAEL

ToBRFV belongs to the *Tobamovirus* genus, which are mechanically transmitted seed-borne viruses preserved in soil containing plant debris from a growth cycle of virus-infected susceptible tomato crops. We have shown that ToBRFV preservation in soil as an infectious pathogen could last ~10 months and we have shown soil mediated infection of tomato plants by ToBRFV contaminated soil. Using a chemical disinfection strategy, we have found that the best results were obtained by treatment of a soil inoculum with 3% chlorinated Trisodium Phosphate (Cl-TSP, a disinfectant) without causing damage to the tomato plants. We are currently performing a physical disinfection strategy using solarization and we aim to reduce profoundly the use of chemicals as disinfectants. A combination of solarization with chemical supplementation may reduce the necessary solarization temperature and/or required time-period.

5.1 Material and methods

5.1.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate

In spring 2023 and spring 2024, in all of our experiments we used nursery supplied tomato seedlings cv 'Ikram' that were grown in coconut coir medium. In general, we planted 4 seedlings in each growbag, 3-5 growbags per tested treatment and hence 12-20 plants per treatment

ToBRFV infection was conducted 14 days post planting by mechanical inoculation with extracts of infected plants. Plants were cultivated for another three to four months. The infection status of the plants was confirmed 30-40 days post inoculation via ELISA using ToBRFV specific antibodies. The non-infected control was grown separately adjacently to minimize contamination.

5.1.2 Solarisation

The solarisation process was performed during August to October. In the 2023 experiment, the solarization was performed in an open area exposed to the sky. The growbags were covered with 40 µm polyethylene plastic film and were connected to drip irrigation (4 drippers per a growbag). Temperatures of the medium were tracked by inserting a datalogger in a selected growbag in each treatment (Figure 6).

Additionally, 12 bags were treated by application of 3% Cl-TSP two weeks after solarization. Another variant was the application of 3% Cl-TSP without prior solarization (12 bags). The 10 bags of the untreated control were left uncovered at 25 °C in a temperature-controlled Chamber/greenhouse with no record of the medium temperature.

5.1.3 Assessment of successful disinfection

To assess if the treatments successfully eradicated ToBRFV:

1. prior to seedling planting in the treated growbags, soil samples were collected and tested for the local lesion assay using *Nicotiana glutinosa* plants.

- tomato seedlings variety cv. 'Ikram' were root truncated (mechanically damaged for increased susceptibility to ToBRFV infection) and planted in the treated growbags/medium at the different time points after treatment (0, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 weeks).

For all treatments, the plants were grown for 40 days and leaf samples were collected and tested for the presence of ToBRFV using ELISA. For the 2024 solarization experiments we added a treatment inside the net-house.

Table 1. A general scheme that illustrates the 2023 solarization experiments.

Weeks after solarisation / Treatment	0	2	4	6	8	10
Positive control	X3	X3	X3	X3	X3	X3
3% CI-TSP		CI-TSP application	X3	X3	X3	X3
Solarization			X3	X3	X3	X3
Solarization +3% CI-TSP		CI-TSP application	X3	X3	X3	X3
Negative control	X2		X2	X2	X2	X2

Figure 6. Illustration of the experimental design for the 2023 Solarization experiments.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Generation of Tobamovirus-contaminated substrate

All the ToBRFV inoculated plants were symptomatic and ELISA positive for ToBRFV.

5.2.2 Solarisation

Temperatures up to 70 °C were reached in the medium during the solarisation treatment. With a minimum of nine to ten hours per day for about 8 weeks. Although we found that 90 °C is preferable to inactivate the virus, lower temperatures however may be efficient but require a longer exposure time for complete virus inactivation.

Figure 7. The 2024 Solarization experiment (July-November/December) in soilless medium

5.2.3 Assessment of successful disinfection

Unfortunately, the experiment of 2023 could not be completed. Currently the 2024 solarization experiments are completed and we are evaluating the soil collected samples using the bio assay (local lesion assay on *N. glutinosa*) and planting the tomato seedlings has already been conducted and requires 40 days for symptom development and ELISA analysis.

5.3 Discussion

Because of the October war in Israel, students were drafted and the biological test of 2023 was not completed sufficiently for drawing conclusions. However, we noticed that no infected tomato plants were detected following 8 and 10 weeks of solarization. Interestingly, a combination of solarization followed by 3% CI-TSP application (at week 2) showed earlier disinfection occurring at 6 weeks of the dual treatments.

Therefore, we are now at the end of another experimental setup for the 2024 summer. The data will be completed at the end of November-December 2024.

6 LUMINEX AND BIOASSAYS BY WAGENINGEN RESEARCH

The Luminex xTag technology is a methodology that has successfully been employed by Wageningen Research for the multiplex detection of plant viruses and viroid targets (Bergervoet *et al.* 2008: doi:10.1016/j.jviromet.2008.01.020; Van Brunschot *et al.* 2014a: doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0084743; 2014b: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jviromet.2013.12.014>; Boonham *et al.* 2014: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.virusres.2013.12.007>). Multiplex in this respect means that a significant number of targets (up to 50) can simultaneously be detected in one sample and in one assay.

Using this multiplex capability of the Luminex xTAG platform, WR has developed an assay that can detect intact plant virus RNA and distinguish it from degraded plant virus RNA. This assay can therefore show the presence or absence of infectious virus.

The method (Figure 8) is based on the amplification of multiple large RT-PCR fragments of plant virus RNA (up to 2,5 Kb in size) ideally covering > 80% of the virus genome. Subsequently from each of these fragments, multiple linear biotin-labeled PCR products are generated in a TSPE step and hybridized to MagPlex paramagnetic beads. In a subsequent detection step, both the beads and any fluorescent signal residing on them is detected. The level of fluorescence is indicative of the amount of virus present in the sample and the multiple signals required for a positive test result add reliability to the assay result.

The two most used methodologies for virus detection, DAS-ELISA, which detects viral coat protein, and RT-qPCR ('TaqMan') that is aimed at detecting very small viral RNA fragments, will also generate positive test results in case of degraded and non-infectious virus. Our Luminex xTAG assay will only result in positive signals in the case of intact and infectious virus RNA.

Figure 8. The different steps in the multiplex xTAG assay.

6.1 Materials and methods

6.1.1 Virus isolate

Virus isolate tomato mosaic virus Ohio III (ToMV-O3, McRitchie and Alexander, 1962) from the plant virus collection of Wageningen Research (WR) was supplied to project partners for the inoculation of tomato material in their steaming and solarization trials.

Based on historical data this virus isolate was classified as tomato mosaic virus (ToMV). In preparation of the development of the Luminex assay and following the supply of this isolate to the project partners, a more detailed genetic analysis of this isolate using High Throughput sequencing (HTS), revealed that it was more closely related to tobacco mosaic virus (TMV). For practical reasons and the fact that ToMV and TMV are both physically, serologically and genetically very closely related, it was decided to continue the trials with this isolate. For clarity this isolate will be referred to as ToMV-O3 which is also the designation under which this isolate can be obtained from the public plant virus collection at WR (www.primediagnosics.com).

ToMV-O3 was mechanically inoculated and maintained on *Nicotiana tabacum* 'White Burley'. Systemically infected leaves were harvested about 2 weeks post inoculation. Leaf material was homogenized in Phosphate buffer at a 1:10 ratio (w/v) and briefly centrifuged to pellet plant material. The supernatant was aliquoted in 1.5 ml Eppendorf tubes which were subsequently stored at -20 °C.

6.1.2 RT-PCR

The RNA sequence of ToMV-O3 multiple primer pairs were used to develop multiple primer pairs aimed to amplify larger RT-PCR fragments between 1.5 and 2.5 Kb. Three primer pairs were selected based on specificity and selectivity. For each of the 3 fragments to be amplified multiple Template Specific primers (TSP) were designed. This resulted in a total of 11 TSP primers to be used in the TSPE (template specific primer extension) reaction.

6.1.3 RNA extractions

Total RNA was extracted from 100 ul of semi-purified ToMV-O3 inoculum or PBS ground tomato root material obtained from the steaming trials of LNW using the Favorgen Plant total RNA purification Mini kit (www.favorgen.com). RNA was eluted in a final volume of 25µl RNase-free MQ. RNA material of the leaf and substrate samples from the solarization trial performed by TEC was supplemented by Scientia Terrae. Total RNA of these samples was extracted using the Qiagen plant Rneasy kit.

6.1.4 DAS-ELISA

DAS-ELISA tests were performed according to standard protocols using 1:1000 dilutions (v/v) of coating and conjugate antisera specific for ToMV-O3 (www.primediagnosics.com).

6.1.5 Luminex xTAG assay

For the Luminex xTAG assay the initial multiplex one-tube RT-PCR was performed in 25 µl reactions with three different ToMV-O3 specific primer sets. 1 µl of total RNA was mixed with 6 µl of MQ, heated for 3' at 60°C and snap-cooled on ice. To each reaction 19 µl of reaction mix was added containing 5 µl of AMV/Tfl 5x buffer, 1 ul 25 mM MgSO₄, 0.5 µl dNTP mix (10mM each), 1 ul of each Forward and Reverse primer (10 µM), 0.25 µl AMV-reverse transcriptase, 0.25 µl Tfl polymerase and 6 µl MQ. cDNA was synthesized for 45 minutes at 45 °C directly followed by 2 minutes of denaturation at 94 °C and 40 cycles of 30" at 94°C, 120" at 50°C and 30" at 68 °C.

RT-PCR clean-up reactions, TSPE reactions, bead hybridization and subsequent detection of fluorescent signals was essentially done as described by van Brunshot et al. 2014 (doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0084743).

6.1.6 Temperature treatments to inactivate virus

Semi-purified virus stock was diluted either 1:100 or 1:400x in 0.01M Phosphate buffer pH7.2 and aliquoted in 200 µl aliquots in 1.5 ml Eppendorf tubes which were subsequently incubated in a dry-heat block for 20 min at either room temperature (RT), 60 °C, 75 °C or 95 °C. After cooling, virus dilutions were directly used for bioassays and stored at -20°C for further serological and molecular analyses.

6.1.7 Virus bioassays

75 µl of heat-treated virus and non-treated virus was inoculated on one half detached leaf of *Nicotina glutinosa*. All half leaves were placed on wet filter paper in a large plastic tray which was subsequently covered with a plastic bag to avoid excessive evaporation. Prior to inoculation, leaves were lightly dusted with carborundum powder and 75µl of virus inoculum or was mechanically inoculated on each half leaf. Leaves were rinsed with tap water 5-10 minutes after inoculation. Local lesions on each half leaf were scored 3 days post inoculation.

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Selection of xTAG primer sets

Ten different ToMV-O3 specific primer sets were initially tested in a simplex setting. This resulted in the selection of three primer sets that showed a good and specific amplification of ToMV-O3 with minimal background and no interference with each other in a multiplex setting. These three primer sets amplified fragments of 1517, 1491 and 1548 bp respectively and were subsequently used for further development of the multiplex xTAG assay. A total of 11 TSPE primers were designed; three for amplicon 1, three for amplicon 2 and four for amplicon 3. None of the amplicon specific TSPE primers showed any cross-reactivity with their non-homologous amplicons and they were successfully tested in a multiplex setting.

6.2.2 Heat inactivation of ToMV-O3

To test the heat inactivation of ToMV-O3 by various temperatures, semi-purified ToMV-O3 was diluted as indicated in the methods section, and the results are presented in Table 2 (see below)

6.2.3 Bioassay of heat-treated ToMV-O3

Detached leaves of *N. glutinosa* were cut in 2 halves along the mid vein. 15 leaf halves were inoculated with 75 µl of each dilution (1:100 and 1:400) of each temperature treatment (60 °C, 75 °C and 95 °C), 10 leaf halves with the RT temperature incubated virus and 5 leaf halves with inoculation buffer as a negative control. Three days after inoculation, local lesions (indicative for infectious virus) were counted on each half leaf (Figure 9). Results are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Local lesions on inoculated *Nicotiana glutinosa* 3 days post inoculation (DPI).

60C	1:100			1:400			75C	1:100			1:400			95C	1:100			1:400		
	leaf no.	60C	RT	buffer	60C	RT		buffer	bladno.	75C	RT	buffer	75C		RT	buffer	bladno.	95C	RT	buffer
1	85	120		11	74		1	1	75		0	10		1	0	31		0	29	
2	89	130		41	36		2	8	25		1	47		2	0	24		0	28	
3	110	56		19	41		3	0	19		4	21		3	0	61		0	12	
4	51	43		11	48		4	5	18		0	37		4	0	115		0	27	
5	50	72		35	40		5	4	20		2	40		5	0	45		0	37	
6	57	140		7	31		6	0	34		0	32		6	0	1		0	40	
7	67	96		30	66		7	3	42		0	4		7	0	51		0	11	
8	94	85		8	20		8	3	43		1	14		8	0	27		0	59	
9	25	10		9	44		9	0	8		0	39		9	0	51		0	28	
10	63	95		26	72		10	1	48		0	25		10	0	48		0	22	
11	48		0	10		0	11	0		0	0		0	11	0		0	0		0
12	69		0	12		0	12	1		0	0		0	12	0		0	0		0
13	40		0	13		0	13	0		0	0		0	13	0		0	0		0
14	63		0	20		0	14	3		0	0		0	14	0		0	0		0
15	72		0	21		0	15	2		0	2		0	15	0		0	0		0
Total	983	847		273	472			31	332		10	269			0	454		0	293	
AVG	65,5	84,7		18,2	47,2			2,1	33,2		0,7	26,9			0,0	29,3		0,0	29,3	
STDEV	22,2	40,7		10,6	18,0			2,3	19,6		1,2	14,4			0,0	14,0		0,0	14,0	

Figure 9. Examples of local lesions on half leaves of *Nicotiana glutinosa* caused by 1:400 (v/v) dilution of semi-purified ToMV-O3 incubated for 20 minutes at 60 °C (left halves) or at room temperature (right halves).

None of the leaves inoculated with the buffer showed any local lesions. The number of lesions was lower on the leaves inoculated with the 1:400 RT positive control in comparison with 1:100 positive control. For the temperature treated virus the results clearly show that a 20-minute incubation at 60 °C already results in a significant reduction of the number of local lesions. At 75 ° C the infectivity of ToMV-O3 is almost gone and at after 20 minutes at 95 °C virus infectivity is completely lost.

6.2.4 Luminex testing of heat-inactivated, steamed and solarized material

The material resulting from the disinfection trial by Tecnova and LNW as described above and the heat-treated semi-purified ToMV-O3 (WR) was tested by the Luminex assay developed and the LNW material was also assessed for infectivity through a bioassay (see 6.2.5). From Tecnova only five samples were received (Tef 1-5), each was an RNA extract from pooled plant material. From LNW both steamed and un-steamed substrate material (cocopeat) with tomato root material was received.

From the LNW material a random selection of 10 samples was made from both the steamed and un-steamed material. Approximately 200-300 mg of root material was carefully taken from the substrate, and ground in PBS in separate extraction bags to avoid cross-contamination. 100µl of each extract was used for a total RNA extraction, and extracted RNA was subsequently used in the Luminex assay. Results are shown in Table 3, Figures 10 and 11.

Table 3. LNW samples tested in the Luminex xTAG assay. Treatments C2 and C4 represent two different containers used for the steaming treatment (> 90 °C for five hours, see 3.2.1.2)

Sample	Location	Treatment 1	Treatment 2
S1	Straelen	No virus	No steaming
S2	Straelen	No virus	C2
S3	Straelen	No virus	C4
S10	Straelen	ToMV-O3	C2
S11	Straelen	ToMV-O3	C4
S16	Straelen	ToMV-O3	C2
S20	Straelen	ToMV-O3	No steaming
S22	Straelen	ToMV-O3	C4
S26	Straelen	ToMV-O3	No steaming
S33	Straelen	ToMV-O3	No steaming

Table 4 shows the Mean Fluorescent Intensities (MFI) values for each of the 11 TSPE primers obtained for the samples tested. Sample are considered positive for infectious virus if (nearly) all TSPE primers show a clear positive result. In Table 4 all positive samples are indicated in red. From the solarization assay performed by Tecnova, sample TEF1 is positive and from LNW samples S10 to S33 tested positive. Sample TEF1 was taken from Line 2 of the TEC solarization experiment. The positive result of the Luminex xTag assay thus correlates with the positive result of the TMV PCR performed by Scientia Terrae. Similarly, samples TEF2 – TEF5 tested negative with this test. The heat-treated semi-purified

ToMV-O3 (WR) tested positive for the samples incubated at RT, 60 °C and 75 °C as did the positive control (PC). The negative water control (MQ) and the 95 °C incubated samples tested negative.

Table 4 Mean fluorescent Intensities (MFI) values for the 11 TSPE primers in the Luminex assay on samples TEF1-5 (Tecnova), S1-S33 (LKW) and heat-incubated semi-purified ToMV-O3 (WR); Negative assay values are indicated in green.

Sample	Amp1-TSP01	Amp1-TSP02	Amp1-TSP03	Amp2-TSP01	Amp2-TSP02	Amp2-TSP03	Amp2-TSP04	Amp3-TSP01	Amp3-TSP03	Amp3-TSP04	Amp3-TSP05
TEF 1	55	593	1349,5	2775	906	467	466	181	488	1740	352,5
TEF 2	14	16	19	20,5	21	18	16	31	13,5	20	17
TEF 3	15	16	19	14	20	18	17,5	21	11	22	18
TEF 4	16	18	20,5	47,5	35	20,5	19	97	15	21	18
TEF 5	14	18	21	16	20	17	18	19	12	20	18
S1	12	16	18	15	17	16	17	19	14	18	17
S2	14	15	20	15	17,5	15	19	17	11	19	16
S3	12,5	14	16,5	14,5	16,5	15	16	17	14	19	16
S10	176,5	2784,5	4526	5142	1703	937	894	583	1108,5	4076,5	755
S11	115	2432	4072	4366	1401,5	754	679	388	933	3936	685
S22	133	2119	4173	4729	1454,5	671	673	533	1008,5	3455,5	603
S16	146	2317	4124	4856	1517	652,5	699	516	961	3437	651,5
S20	127,5	2163	3972	4375,5	1238	585,5	639	432	880	3360,5	635
S26	143,5	2255,5	4077	5142	1589	679	708	572	1080	3480	628
S33	125	70	257	5152	1615,5	173	91,5	611	392	73,5	35
Kt	120,5	3248	5305	5196,5	1730	891,5	1144	532	1095	3883	802
60°C	113	2042	3798,5	5293	1785	938	1105	611	1229	4015,5	859
75°C	81	282	895,5	5520	1553	390	402,5	849	1385	1679,5	303
95°C	21	25	55	1077	279,5	18	18	134	26	19	19
PC	67	1034	2765	6811	2540	1350,5	1251	700	1456	4570	1000
MQ	11	16	19	14	17	15	19	17,5	10	19	13

6.2.5 Additional testing of heat-inactivated, steamed and solarized material

Following the testing of the material in the Luminex assays, the samples were additionally tested by more conventional virus assays. For the samples from Tecnova, LNW and WR, RNA was available and tested in a SYBR Green RT-qPCR assay. As can be seen from Figure 10 the results from the RT-qPCR coincide with the results previously obtained in the Luminex assay.

Figure 10. Amplification plot and Ct values of the SYBER-Green RT-qPCR results of the tested samples. Ct-values >36 are considered negative.

KT	26,1
60C	25,8
75C	25,8
95C	37,2
S1	38,7
S2	N/A
S3	N/A
S10	22,7
S11	20,7
S16	22,2
S20	23,1
S22	20,5
S26	21,4
S33	20,8
TEF 1	31,9
TEF 2	20,7
TEF 3	21,3
TEF 4	18,8
TEF 5	N/A
ToMV-O3	23,6
MQ	N/A

For the samples from LNW and WR also plant sap was available and these were tested in a DAS-ELISA using ToMV-O3 specific antisera. Both 1:100 and 1:400 dilutions of the heat-treated semi-purified ToMV-O3 as well as 10x and 50x times dilutions from the root extracts from LNW were tested, all in duplicate (see Table 5).

Table 5: Set-up of samples in an ELISA plate with WR samples (RT, 60C - 95C) and LNW samples (S1 to S33). NC = negative control, SEB = Sample Elisa Buffer.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB
B	NC	RT 100x	RT 100x	95C 100x	95C 100x	S3 10x	S3 10x	S16 10x	S16 10x	S26 10x	S26 10x	SEB
C	NC	RT 400x	KR 400x	95C 400x	95C 400x	S3 50x	S3 50x	S16 50x	S16 50x	S26 50x	S26 50x	SEB
D	NC	60C 100x	60C 100x	S1 10x	S1 10x	S10 10x	S10 10x	S20 10x	S20 10x	S33 10x	S33 10x	SEB
E	NC	60C 400x	60C 400x	S1 50x	S1 50x	S10 50x	S10 50x	S20 50x	S20 50x	S33 50x	S33 50x	SEB
F	NC	75C 100x	75C 100x	S2 10x	S2 10x	S11 10x	S11 10x	S22 10x	S22 10x	PC ToMV-O3	PC ToMV-O3	SEB
G	NC	75C 400x	75C 400x	S2 50x	S2 50x	S11 50x	S11 50x	S22 50x	S22 50x	-	-	SEB
H	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB

Table 6 summarizes the DAS-ELISA results. ELISA results were marked positive if their values exceeded the average of the NC plus three times the standard deviation of the NC. Clearly positive ELISA results are indicated in red. Only one of the duplicates of LNW sample S1 (no virus) showed a very light positive reaction (0.079 with threshold = 0.072). Results show that all heat-treated ToMV-O3 samples were highly positive in the DAS-ELISA but also that the LNW samples, both the steamed (S10, S11, S16, S22) as well as the un-steamed (S20, S26, S33) are all clearly positive in ELISA.

These ELISA results are as expected. Disinfection of tobamovirus through prolonged high temperatures will result in break-down of virus particles but the viral coat protein will stay intact and can still be detected through DAS-ELISA).

Table 6. DAS-ELISA results of WR samples (RT, 60C - 95C) and LNW samples (S1 - S33). NC = negative control, SEB = Sample Elisa Buffer. Red cells indicate clear positive results.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB
B	NC	KT 100x	KT 100x	95C 100x	95C 100x	S3 10x	S3 10x	S16 10x	S16 10x	S26 10x	S26 10x	SEB
C	NC	KT 400x	KT 400x	95C 400x	95C 400x	S3 50x	S3 50x	S16 50x	S16 50x	S26 50x	S26 50x	SEB
D	NC	60C 100x	60C 100x	S1 10x	S1 10x	S10 10x	S10 10x	S20 10x	S20 10x	S33 10x	S33 10x	SEB
E	NC	60C 400x	60C 400x	S1 50x	S1 50x	S10 50x	S10 50x	S20 50x	S20 50x	S33 50x	S33 50x	SEB
F	NC	75C 100x	75C 100x	S2 10x	S2 10x	S11 10x	S11 10x	S22 10x	S22 10x	PC ToMV-3	PC ToMV-3	SEB
G	NC	75C 400x	75C 400x	S2 50x	S2 50x	S11 50x	S11 50x	S22 50x	S22 50x			SEB
H	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB	SEB

6.2.6 Bioassay of LNW samples

As expected, both the DAS-ELISA and the RT-qPCR tests showed positive results for the steamed substrate samples S10 to S33 from LNW. Heat treatment will not destroy the virus coat protein which can subsequently still be detected in DAS-ELISA and even degraded. Viral RNA can still be detected in a RT-qPCR assay. However, the Luminex assay showed unexpected positive results for the steamed substrate samples of LNW (S10, S11, S16, S22, see Table 3), as it was expected that the steaming would have degraded the viral RNA.

To test if the steaming in these samples had or had not resulted in destroying the biological activity of the virus the material was tested in a bioassay. Set-up of this assay was basically identical to the bioassay of the heat-treated WR samples. Sample extracts used for the DAS-ELISA and RNA extractions were inoculated on three full leaves of *N. glutinosa* and local lesions were scored 3 days post inoculation (DPI) (Figure 11) *refectious* ToMV-O3 was included as a positive control.

Figure 11: Local lesions on *N. glutinosa* caused by LNW samples S1, S10, S22 and S33 and TMV (PC).

Table 7 lists the total number of local lesions on the three *N. glutinosa* leaves for the 4 LNW samples. S1 (no virus) shows no local lesion, and samples S10, S22 and S33 all show local lesions although significantly less than the ToMV-O3 positive control. These results are in line with the previous Luminex results in which samples S10, S22 and S33 also showed positive TSPE signals – indicative of intact ToMV-O3 RNA – albeit that also these signals were lower than the ToMV-O3 positive control.

Table 7. Number of local lesions on three *N. glutinosa* leaves three days post inoculation with LNW samples S1 to S33 and ToMV-O3 as positive control.

Root sample	S1	S10	S22	S33	ToMV-O3
treatment	No virus	steaming	steaming	No steaming	
LL leaf 1	0	13	5	13	100
LL leaf 2	0	62	6	4	100
LL leaf 3	0	19	18	16	100
Total	0	94	29	33	300

6.3 Discussion

6.3.1 Development of a Luminex xTAG assay to distinguish infectious from non-infectious virus

One prerequisite for a plant virus to be infectious is that its genetic material is intact upon entering a cell as this is needed for replication and translation of this genetic material. An assay was developed that is able to detect the presence or (near) absence of such intact genetic material (in this case RNA). The assay is technically based on the Luminex xTAG system which amplifies multiple large RT-PCR fragments of plant virus RNA which are subsequently detected in a fluorescence-based assay. As this system is multiplex, the assay results depend on the presence or absence of multiple signals increasing reliability of the assay.

This assay was successfully capable of distinguishing infectious ToMV-O3 from non-infectious ToMV-O3 after a heat treatment for 20 minutes at 95 °C. The assay results also indicate that not all virus RNA is degraded after 20 minutes incubation at 60 °C or even 75 °C as these samples still show positive assay results. These assay results were confirmed by a bioassay in which heat-treated virus was inoculated on *N. glutinosa*. Infectious virus causes the formation of local lesions on these leaves and the number of local lesions is an indication of the level of virus infectivity remaining after the heat-treatment. Both the Luminex assay and the accompanying bioassay show that ToMV-O3, as a typical tobamovirus, is extremely resistant to degradation and retains its infectivity also under harsh conditions (i.e. 20 minutes incubation at 75 °C).

In contrast to the Luminex assay both a DAS-ELISA and a RT-qPCR method were clearly positive for all ToMV-O3/TMV samples incubated at 60 °C, 75 °C and 95 °C, indicating they cannot distinguish infectious from non-infectious virus.

6.3.2 Testing of disinfected substrates

Tecnova and LNW performed disinfection assays, using solarization or steaming, respectively, as their means of eliminating ToMV-O3 infectivity on substrates in which ToMV-O3 infected tomato plants were grown. Both partners tested remaining infectivity of ToMV-O3 by replanting bioassays, i.e. growing new healthy tomato plants in disinfected substrates and scoring for typical virus symptoms.

LNW did not find any newly infected plants concluding that a 20-minute period of steaming at 95 °C which was likely to be sufficient to eliminate all infectious virus while dry heating substrate at 95 °C, even at prolonged periods of time may not be sufficient to kill the virus. Tecnova also did not find any plant with typical tobamovirus symptoms after 133 days of solarisation but did show the presence of ToMV-O3 in plants using RT-PCR indicating that not all virus had been eliminated by the solarization.

Material from Tecnova (RNA samples supplied by ST) and LNW (roots from 'virus infected' steamed and un-steamed substrate) was tested in the newly developed Luminex assay. In contrast to the replanting bioassay, the Luminex result did show the presence of intact ToMV-O3 RNA, suggesting not all infectivity had been destroyed by solarisation or steaming.

Therefore, an additional bioassay was performed with the material from LNW in a local lesion assay to verify if indeed infectious material was retained in the disinfected substrates. As no plant material from

the Tecnova solarisation experiment was available anymore, these samples could not be included in the additional bioassays by WR, although ST confirmed the positive detection obtained with their TMV PCR on the leaf sample taken from Line 2 with a bioassay in Xanthi at their facilities. These local lesion assays did show that infectious virus was still present in the steamed and solarized substrates although with a significantly reduced number of infectious particles. This was in line with the previously obtained Luminex results. It is likely that the replanting bioassays by replanting healthy tomato plants may not have been sensitive enough to detect residual infectious virus.

The results from these assays indicate that one must be careful in concluding whether a particular disinfection method is effective in eliminating tobamovirus infectivity. The extremely persistent nature of these viruses in combination with their usually very high titers in infected plant material, makes successful eliminating infectious tobamovirus very difficult.

The Luminex method that was developed can aid in determining the efficacy of particular virus disinfection methods, not only for tobamoviruses but for other plant viruses as well. However, given the significant agronomic and economic damage plant viruses can cause, it is advisable to verify the efficacy of particular disinfection strategies by multiple methods, preferably a combination of the Luminex method with an appropriate bioassay.